

FORMASAM/ISIMIP future forest management scenarios

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General explanations

1. This document complements the ISIMIP2b simulation protocol (<https://www.isimip.org/protocol/2b/>) for the regional forest sector and provides future forest management scenarios for the nine forest sites of the PROFOUND database (Reyer et al. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-1295-2020>). We propose for each PROFOUND site 3-5 management scenarios (Current-Site-Specific, Bioenergy, Harvested Wood Products (HWP) and Multifunctional Adapted). Le Bray has two bioenergy scenarios, Solling Beech has two adaptation scenarios and no HWP scenario, Solling Spruce has no HWP scenario.
2. Transition from historical management to future managements start in 2020. E.g. Bily Kriz is 34 years old in 2015, hence theoretically in 2016 at age 35 the first thinning from the new management should start (15% BA under current site specific management guidelines). Yet, because this is before 2020, it is not included but only the next thinning in 2026 at age 45 (10% BA under current site specific management guidelines is modelled). Exceptions exist for Le-bray and Solling-beech for the current generic scenarios.
3. If models are unable to simulate natural regeneration as a continuous process as required for the Bily Kriz MFA management, the suggestion is to mimic continuous natural regeneration by simulating plantings every 5 years depending on how the model works.
4. When harvesting and planting are scheduled in the same year, i.e. in a sheltercut system, the new stand age starts counting from the planting year. In the subsequent management intervention, usually, the harvesting then takes place and refers to trees still present from the old rotation. The Thinning intensity then refers to the trees of the new rotation. E.g. in Collelongo in 2126, the 95 year old trees are thinned (TB15 under the maximize bioenergy scenario) and at the same time new trees are planted according to the plantation guidelines. Then, in 2141, the 120 year old remaining trees are harvested and the newly planted, 15-year old trees are thinned (TB35).
5. DBH is defined as diameter at breast height of 1.30m

Bily-Kriz

Table 1: Management guidelines for Bily-Kriz.

Scenario [ISIMIP-scenario-name]	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	piab	stem	below	30% BA	120	15 30 45 60 75 90 105	piab	4500	4	0.5	na	9	historical planting density was 5000/ha but current practices are 4500/ha only
No management [nosoc]	na	piab	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	even-aged clearcut	piab	stem	below	50 20 15 10 10 30 40% BA	110	15 25 35 45 60 95 105	piab + NR of fasy & abal (about 5%)	4000/ha piab + 1000/ha fasy + 500/ha abal to mimic NR	4	0.3	na	8	fasy and abal are "allowed" in NR but not managed, only sanitary removal of dead trees, the final cut is split into two (at age 105 and age 110)
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	even-aged clearcut	piab	stem+ branches	below	40% BA	45	20	piab	4000	4	0.3	na	8	regenerate as pure piab stand
HWP [rcp26sochwp / rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]	even-aged clearcut	piab	stem	above	50 20 15 10 10 10 30 40% BA	120	15 25 35 45 60 80 100 110	piab	4000	4	0.3	na	8	thinning from above mimics selection of future crop trees (400 trees per hectare)

Multifunctional-Adapted [rpc26soca / rpc60soca / rpc85soca]	shelterwood transition to mixed selection forest (regenerating continuously, whenever there are gaps)	piab, fasy, abal	stem	Above Above Random Random Above_piab (Target DBH 55cm)/Random_fasy,abal,piab2 Above (Target DBH 55cm)	25 piab 10 piab 15 piab 10 piab, 5 fasy & abal 15 piab, 5 fasy & abal & piab 2 nd generation 15%BA all	after transition: target DBH 55cm	40 45 55 65-75-85 95-105-115-125-135-145 155-165...every 10 years	during transition: planting of fasy & abal + NR of piab, after transition only NR	4000/ha piab + 1000/ha fasy + 500/ha abal to mimic NR	4	0.3	na	8	any species, but mainly piab, fasy, abal are "allowed" in NR
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Table 2: Detailed management schedule for Bily-Kriz. *Ini* = Initialization data, *HM* = Historic Management, *FM* = Future Management, *TB*=Thinning from below, *TA* = Thinning from above, *H*= Harvest, *P*=Planting

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	FM16	FM17	FM18	FM19	Remarks	
Current generic	1997	1998-2015	2030	2045	2060	2075	2090	2100	2101	2116	2131	...	2221	2222	2238	...	2297						
		T	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	H	P	TB30	TB30	TB30	H	P	TB30	TB30	TB30						
Current Site-specific	1997	1998-2015	2026	2041	2076	2086	2091	2092	2107	2117	2127	2137	2152	2187	2197	2202	2203	...	2313				
		T	TB10	TB10	TB30	TB40	H	P	TB50	TB20	TB15	TB10	TB10	TB30	TB40	H	P	...	H				
Bioenergy	1997	1998-2015	2026	2027	2047	2072	2073	2093	2118	2119	2139	2164	2165	2185	2210	2211	2231	2256	2257	...	2302		
		T	H	P	TB40	H	P	TB40	H	P	TB40	H	P	TB40	H	P	TB40	H	P		H		
HWP	1997	1998-2015	2026	2041	2061	2081	2091	2101	2102	2117	2127	2137	2147	2162	2182	2202	2212	2222	2223	...	2303		
		T	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA30	TA40	H	P	TA50	TA20	TA15	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA30	TA40	H	P	...	TA10		
Multifunctional-Adapted	1997	1998-2015	2021	2026	2036	2046	2056	2066	2076	2086	2096	2106	2116	2126	2136	2146	2156	2166	2176	..	2306	special settings as continuous cover forestry is implemented	
		T	TA25	TA10	T15	T10			TA15, NR					TA15, NR					Spruce management				
						NR			T05					TA15, NR					2 nd generation Spruce management				
			P			T05, NR							TA15, NR					Beech and Abies management					

Collelongo

Table 3: Management guidelines for Collelongo.

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	fasy	stem	above	30% BA	140	15 30 45 60 75 90 105 120 135	fasy	10000	4	1.3	0.1	4	the planting data is only a rough approximation, usually NR is the regeneration method
No management [nosoc]	na	fasy	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	shelterwood (start regenerating at age 105)	fasy	stem	below below below below above	35% 25% 25% 25% 35% BA	120	15 35 60 85 105	fasy	NR 9000 (8000-10000)	1	0.1	0.1	5	the first thinning is precommercial, The planting data is only a rough approximation, usually NR is the regeneration method.
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	shelterwood (start regenerating at age 105)	fasy	stem+ branches	below	35% 15% 15% 15% 15% 15% BA	120	15 35 55 75 95 105	fasy	NR 9000 (8000-10000)	1	0.1	0.1	5	the planting data is only a rough approximation, usually NR is the regeneration method.
HWP [rcp26sochwp / rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]	shelterwood (start regenerating at age 140)	fasy	stem	below below below below above above	35% 25% 25% 25% 35% 35% BA	160	15 35 60 85 105 140	fasy	NR 9000 (8000-10000)	1	0.1	0.1	5	the planting data is only a rough approximation, usually NR is the regeneration method.

Multifunctional-Adapted [rcp26soca / rcp60soca / rcp85soca]	even-aged clearcut	fasy + qupu	stem	below	fasy:	120		fasy + qupu	400	3	0.5	1	5	
				below	35%		15	400 qupu, NR with fasy approximated using 600 samplings						
				below	15%		35							
				below	15%		55							
				below	15%		75							
				below	15%		95							
				above	15% BA		105							
					qupu:									
				below	40%		15							
				below	20%		35							
				below	20%		55							
				below	20%		75							
below	20%		95											
above	20% BA		105											

Table 4: Detailed management schedule for Collelongo. *Ini* = Initialization data, *HM* = Historic Management, *FM* = Future Management, *TB*=Thinning from below, *TA* = Thinning from above, *H*= Harvest, *P*=Planting

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	FM16	FM17	FM18	FM19	FM20	FM21	Remarks	
Current Generic	1992	1997-2012	2027	2032	2033	2048	2063	2078	2093	...	2258	2173	2174	2189	...	2294									
		T	TA30	H	P	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	H	P	TA30		TA30									
Current Site-specific	1992	1997-2012	2020	2021	2036	2056	2081	2106	2126	2141	2161	2186	2211	2231	2246	2266	2286								
		T	H	P	TB35	TB25	TB25	TB25	TA35, P	H, TB35	TB25	TB25	TB25	TA35, P	H, TB35	TB35	TB25								
Bioenergy	1992	1997-2012	2020	2021	2036	2056	2076	2096	2116	2126	2141	2161	2181	2201	2221	2231	2246	2266	2286						
		T	H	P	TB35	TB15	TB15	TB15	TB15	TB15, P	H, TB35	TB15	TB15	TB15	TB15	TB15, P	H, TB35	TB15	TB15						
HWP	1992	1997-2012	2032	2052	2053	2068	2088	2113	2138	2158	2193	2213*	2228	2253	2278	2298									
		T	TA35	H	P	TB35	TB25	TB25	TB25	TA35	TA35, P	H, TB35	TB25	TB25	TB25	TA35									
Multifunctional-Adapted	1992	1997-2012	2020	2021	2036	2056	2076	2096	2116	2126	2141	2142	2157	2177	2197	2217	2237	2247	2262	2263	2278	2298	2318		
		T	H	P	TB35, TB40	TB15, TB20	TB15, TB20	TB15, TB20	TB15, TB20	TA15, TA20	H	P	TB35, TB40	TB15, TB20	TB15, TB20	TB15, TB20	TB15, TB20	TA15, TA20	H	P	TB35, TB40	TB15, TB20	TB15, TB20	first number fasy, second qupu	

*exceptionally this thinning happens at age 20 and not age 15

Hyytiälä

Table 5: Management guidelines for Hyytiälä.

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem	below	20% BA	140	15 30 45 60 75 90 105 120 135	pisy	2250 (2000-2500)	2	0.25 (0.2-0.3)	na	6 (5-7)	regenerate as pure pisy stand
No management [nosoc]	na	pisy	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem	below below above	20% BA	90	20 50 70	pisy	2000	2	0.25 (0.2-0.3)	na	7 (5-7)	regenerate as pure pisy stand
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem+ branches	below	25% BA	60	20	pisy	2500	2	0.25 (0.2-0.3)	na	8 (5-7)	regenerate as pure pisy stand
HWP [rcp26sochwp / rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem	below below above above	10% BA	120	20 50 70 110	pisy	2500	2	0.25 (0.2-0.3)	na	9 (5-7)	regenerate as pure pisy stand
Multifunctional-Adapted [rcp26soca / rcp60soca / rcp85soca]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem	below below above	20% BA	80	20 40 60	pisy	2000 +NR	2	0.25 (0.2-0.3)	na	10 (5-7)	regenerate as pure pisy stand

Table 6: Detailed management schedule for Hyytiälä. *Ini* = Initialization data, *HM* = Historic Management, *FM* = Future Management, *TB*=Thinning from below, *TA* = Thinning from above, *H*= Harvest, *P*=Planting

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	FM16	FM17	FM18	FM19	Remarks
Current generic	1995	1996-2011	2026	2041	2056	2071	2086	2101	2102	2117	...	2242	2243	2258	...							Only simulate pine and spruce (no hardwoods) and regenerate as pure pine stand.
		T	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	TB20	TB20	H	P	TB20	TB20							
Current Site-specific	1995	1996-2011	2031	2051	2052	2072	2102	2122	2142	2143	2163	2193	2213	2233	2234	2254	2284	2304				
		T	TA20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TA20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TA20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TA20				
Bioenergy	1995	1996-2011	2021	2022	2042	2082	2083	2103	2143	2144	2164	2204	2205	2225	2265	2266	2286	2326				
		T	H	P	TB25	H																
HWP	1995	1996-2011	2031	2071	2081	2082	2102	2132	2152	2192	2202	2203	2223	2253	2273	2313						
		T	TA10	TA10	H	P	TB10	TB10	TA10	TA10	H	P	TB10	TB10	TA10	TA10						
Multifunctional-Adapted	1995	1996-2011	2021	2041	2042	2062	2082	2102	2122	2123	2143	2163	2183	2203	2204	2224	2244	2264	2284	2285	2305	
		T	TA20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TA20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TA20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TA20	H	P	TB20	

Kroof (mixed beech & spruce forest)

Table 7: Management guidelines for Kroof (beech).

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	fasy	stem	above	30% BA	140	15 30 45 60 75 90 105 120 135	fasy	6000 (5000-7000)	2	0.6 (0.5-0.7)	na	5	the planting density is for single-species stands, hence when regenerating the stand as a 2-species-stand (fasy, piab), the planting density of each species should be halved
No management [nosoc]	na	fasy	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	target DBH mimicked through rotation length	fasy	stem	above	15% BA	120	20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100 110	NR; fasy	4000 after 10 years (2500-5000)	2	0.6 (0.5-0.7)	na	7	the planting density is a 2-species-stand (fasy,piab), planting density for a single stand should be doubled
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	target DBH mimicked through rotation length	fasy	stem + branches	above	15% BA	80	20 25 30 35 40 45 50 60 70	NR; fasy	4000 after 10 years (2500-5000)	2	0.6 (0.5-0.7)	na	7	the planting density is a 2-species-stand (fasy,piab), planting density for a single stand should be doubled

HWP [rpc26sochwp / rpc60sochwp / rpc85sochwp]	target DBH mimicked through rotation length	fasy	stem	above	10% BA	130	20 30 35 40 45 50 55 60 70 80 90 100 110 120	NR; fasy	4000 after 10 years (2500- 5000)	2	0.6 (0.5- 0.7)	na	7	the planting density is a 2-species-stand (fasy,piab), planting density for a single stand should be doubled
Multifunctional-Adapted [rpc26soca / rpc60soca / rpc85soca]	Same as Current Site-specific													

Table 8: Management guidelines for Kroof (spruce).

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	piab	stem	below	30% BA	120	15 30 45 60 75 90 105	piab	2250 (2000-2500)	2	0.35 (0.3-0.4)	na	7	the planting density is for single-species stands, hence when regenerating the stand as a 2-species-stand (fasy, piab), the planting density of each species should be halved
No management [nosoc]	na	piab	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	target DBH mimicked through rotation length	piab	stem	above	12.5% BA	90	10 25 30 35 40 45 55 65 75	piab	1500 (1000-2000)	2	0.35 (0.3-0.4)	na	5	the planting density is for single-species stands, hence when regenerating the stand as a 2-species-stand (fasy, piab), the planting density of each species should be halved, planting is delayed until beech is also planted
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	target DBH mimicked through rotation length	piab	stem + branches	below	10% BA	50	15 25 35 45	piab	1500 (1000-2000)	2	0.35 (0.3-0.4)	na	5	the planting density is a 2-species-stand (fasy, piab), planting density for a single stand should be doubled, planting is delayed until beech is also planted
HWP [rcp26sochwp / rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]	target DBH mimicked through rotation length	piab	stem	above	7.5% BA	110	10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90	piab	1500 (1000-2000)	2	0.35 (0.3-0.4)	na	5	the planting density is a 2-species-stand (fasy, piab), planting density for a single stand should be doubled, planting is delayed until beech is also planted

Multifunctional-
Adapted
[rcp26soca /
rcp60soca /
rcp85soca]

Same as Current Site-specific

Table 9: Detailed management schedule for Kroof (beech+spruce). Ini = Initialization data, HM = Historic Management, FM = Future Management, TB=Thinning from below, TA = Thinning from above, H= Harvest, P=Planting, ***plantings are delayed until beech is also harvested to harmonize the planting dates.

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	FM16	FM17	FM18	FM19	FM20	FM21	FM22	FM23	FM24	Remarks	
Current Generic	1997	1999-2010	2025	2040	2055	2070	2085	2100	2101	2102	2117	...	2222	2223	2238	...											Beech part of stand, maximum age extended a bit to avoid harvesting just before the end of the simulation	
		T	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	H	P	TA30	TA30	H	P	TA30	TA30											
	1997	1999-2010	2025	2040	2055	2070	2085	2100	2101	2102	2117	...	2222	2223	2238	...												Spruce part of stand, maximum age extended a bit to avoid harvesting just before the end of the simulation
		T	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	H	P	TB30	TB30	H	P	TB30	TB30											
Current Site-specific		1999-2010	2023	2033	2043	2053	2063	2064	2084	2094	2104	2114	2124	2134	2144	2154	2164	2174	2184	2185	...	2295						Beech part of stand
		T	TA15	TA15	TA15	TA15	H	P	TA15	TA15	TA15	TA15	H	P	...	TA15												
		1999-2010	2025	2040	2064	2074	2089	2094	2099	2104	2109	2119	2129	2139	2154	2185	...	2275										Spruce part of stand
	1997	T	TA12.5	H	P***	TA12.5	H	P***	...	H																		
Bio-energy		1999-2010	2023	2024	2044	2049	2054	2059	2064	2069	2074	2084	2094	2104	2105	...	2185	2186	...	2266	2267	...	2297					Beech part of stand
		T	H	P	TA15	TA15	TA15	TA15	TA15	TA15	TA15	TA15	TA15	H	P	...	H	P	...	H	P	...	TA15					
		1999-2010	2020	2024	2039	2049	2059	2069	2074	2105	2120	2130	2140	2150	2155	2186	...	2236	2267	...	2292							Spruce part of stand
	1997	T	H	P***	TB10	TB10	TB10	TB10	H	P***	TB10	TB10	TB10	TB10	H	P***	...	H	P***	...	TB10							
HWP	1997	1999-2010	2023	2033	2043	2053	2063	2073	2074	2094	2104	2109	2114	2119	2124	2129	2134	2144	2154	2164	2174	2184	2194	2204	2205	...	Beech part of stand	

		T	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	H	P	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	H	P	...								
		1999-2010	2020	2030	2040	2060	2074	2084	2094	2104	2114	2124	2134	2144	2154	2164	2184	2205	...	2295								Spruce part of stand
		T	TA7.5	TA7.5	TA7.5	H	P***	TA7.5	H	P***	...	TA7.5																

Le-bray

Table 10: Management guidelines for Le-bray.

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	pipi	stem	below	20% BA	45	10 20 30 40	pipi	1250 (1000-14000)	1	0.2 (0.1-0.25)	na	3 (2-5)	these are the current practices (De Lary, 2015) and should be used for future regeneration. Historically, the site was seeded with 3000-5000 seedlings per ha and then cleared once or twice to reach a density of 1250/ha at 7-year old when seedlings reach the size for DBH recruitment. If a model requires to be initialised at planting for the historical simulations as well. modelers could mimic this by "planting" trees with DBH of 7.5cm and 6m height in 1978 with a density of 1250 trees/ha
No management [nosoc]	na	pipi	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	even-aged clearcut	pipi	stem	below	20% BA	45	10 20 30 40	pipi	2500	1	0.1	na	7	this is to mimic the change in managed from sowing to planting, timing of thinnings and final cut is mimicking a target-oriented harvesting schedule.
Bioenergy-flexible [rcp26socbef / rcp60socbef / rcp85socbef]	even-aged clearcut	pipi	stem+ branches+ stump	below	50% 20% 20% 20% BA	45	7 12 20 30 40	pipi	2500	1	0.1	na	7	stumps only harvested after final cut, not after thinnings

Bioenergy-biomass [rcp26socbeb / rcp60socbeb / rcp85socbeb]	even-aged clearcut	pipi	stem+ branches+ stump	below	na	30	na	pipi	2500	1	0.1	na	7	stumps only harvested after final cut, not after thinnings
HWP [rcp26sochwp / rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]	even-aged clearcut	pipi	stem	below	15% BA	60	15 30 40 50	pipi	1600	1	0.1	na	7	
Multifunctional- Adapted [rcp26soca / rcp60soca / rcp85soca]	even-aged clearcut	pipi	stem	below	30% BA	45	10 20 30 40	pipi	1250	1	0.1	na	7	

Table 11: Detailed management schedule for Le-bray. *Ini* = Initialization data, *HM* = Historic Management, *FM* = Future Management, *TB*=Thinning from below, *TA* = Thinning from above, *H*= Harvest, *P*=Planting

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	FM16	FM17	FM18	FM19	FM20	Remarks
Current generic	1986	1987-2009	2015	2016	2026	2036	2046	2056	2061	2062	2072	...	2107	2108	2118	...	2153	...	2199	...	2245	...	
		T	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	TB20	TB20	H	P	TB20	TB20	H	TB20	H	TB20	H	TB20	
Current Site-specific	1986	1987-2009	2020	2021	2031	2041	2051	2061	2066	2067	2077	2087	2097	2107	2112	2113	...	2158	...	2203	...	2295	
		T	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	...	H	...	H	...	H	
Bioenergy-flexible	1986	1987-2009	2020	2021	2028	2033	2041	2051	2061	2066	2067	2074	2079	2087	2097	2107	2112	2113	...	2158	...	2295	
		T	H	P	TB50	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	TB50	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	...	H	...	H	
Bioenergy-biomass	1986	1987-2009	2020	2021	2051	2052	2082	2083	2113	2114	2144	2145	2175	2176	2206	2207	2237	2238	2268	...	2300		
		T	H	P	H	P	H	P	H	P	H	P	H	P	H	P	H	P	H		P		
HWP	1986	1987-2009	2020	2030	2031	2046	2061	2071	2081	2091	2092	2107	2122	2132	2142	2152	2153	...	2274	2275	...	2305	
		T	TB15	H	P	TB15	TB15	TB15	TB15	H	P	TB15	TB15	TB15	TB15	H	P		H	P	...	TB15	
Multifunctional-Adapted	1986	1987-2009	2020	2021	2031	2041	2051	2061	2066	2067	2077	2087	2097	2107	2112	2213	...	2258	2259	...	2304		
		T	H	P	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	H	P	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	H	P	...	H	P	...	H		

Peitz

Table 12: Management guidelines for Peitz.

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem	below	20% BA	140	15 30 45 60 75 90 105 120 135	pisy	9000 (8000-10000)	2	0.175 (0.1-0.25)	na	5	The "age when DBH is reached = 5" is an estimate
No management [nosoc]	na	pisy	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem	below below above	10% 20% 20% BA	120	55 75 95	pisy	9000	2	0.175 (0.1-0.25)	na	5	regenerate as pure pisy stand
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem+ branches	below (pulp+ bioenergy)	25% BA	95	55	pisy	7000	2	0.175 (0.1-0.25)	na	5	regenerate as pure pisy stand
HWP [rcp26sochwp / rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]	even-aged clearcut	pisy	stem	below below above above	10% BA	120	20 50 70 110	pisy	9000	2	0.175 (0.1-0.25)	na	5	regenerate as pure pisy stand
Multifunctional-Adapted [rcp26soca / rcp60soca / rcp85soca]	even-aged clearcut with few remaining seed trees	pisy	stem	below below above	15% BA	100	40 60 80	pisy, quro/qupe, bepe in NR	4000 (pisy) +1500 (qupe/qupo) +1500 (bepe)	2	0.175 (0.1-0.25)	na	5	qupe/quro, fasy, rops, bepe allowed in NR

Table 13: Detailed management schedule for Peitz. Ini = Initialization data, HM = Historic Management, FM = Future Management, TB=Thinning from below, TA = Thinning from above, H= Harvest, P=Planting. **= some GCM data only starts in 1950, hence for future runs, you have to initialize these forests at the first time step after 1949 (i.e. 1952 for Peitz). For the historical validation runs you can start with the first available stand initialization.

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	Remarks
Current Generic	1948* *	1952- 2011	2026	2040	2041	2056	2071	2086	2101	...	2181	2182	2197	...				
		T	TB20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	TB20	TB20				
Current Site-specific	1948* *	1952- 2011	2020	2021	2076	2096	2116	2141	2142	2197	2217	2237	2262	2263	2318			
		T	H	P	TB10	TB20	TA20	H	P	TB10	TB20	TA20	H	P	TB10			
Bioenergy	1948* *	1952- 2011	2020	2021	2076	2116	2117	2172	2212	2213	2268	2308						
		T	H	P	TB25	H	P	TB25	H	P	TB25	H						
HWP	1948* *	1952- 2011	2020	2021	2041	2071	2091	2131	2141	2142	2162	2192	2212	2252	2262	2263	2283	
		T	H	P	TB10	TB10	TA10	TA10	H	P	TB10	TB10	TA10	TA10	H	P	TB10	
Multifunctional-Adapted	1948* *	1952- 2011	2020	2021	2061	2081	2101	2121	2122	2162	2182	2202	2222	2223P	2263	2283	2303	
		T	H	P	TB15	TB15	TA15	H	P	TB15	TB15	TA15	H	P	TB15	TB15	TA15	

Solling-beech

Table 14: Management guidelines for Solling-beech.

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	fasy	stem	above	30% BA	140	15 30 45 60 75 90 105 120 135	fasy	6000 (5000-7000)	2	0.6 (0.5-0.7)	na	5	The actual stand was established in 1847 from natural regeneration. Until begin of measurements in 1966, the stand was regularly thinned. All figures in table are estimates. Natural regeneration is the recommended regeneration method of stand establishment; stem count in 2014: 130
No management [nosoc]	na	fasy	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	even-aged clearcut	fasy	stem	above above above above above above above above above below below	20% BA	120	5 10 15 20 25 30 35 50 65 80 95 110	fasy	8500 (7000-10000)	2	0.3 (0.2-0.4)	na	4	
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	even-aged clearcut	fasy	stem+ branches	below	30% BA	90	45	fasy	8500 (7000-10000)	2	0.3 (0.2-0.4)	na	4	
HWP [rcp26sochwp /	same as Current Site-specific													

rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]														
Multifunctional-Adapted [rcp26soca / rcp60soca / rcp85soca]	even-aged clearcut transition to mixed forest with psme	fasy (40%) + psme (60%)	stem	above above above above above above below below	20% BA	90	5 10 15 20 25 30 35 50 65 80	fasy + psme	4000 (3500-4500) fasy + 6000 (5000-7000) psme	2	0.3 (0.2-0.4)	na	4	
Multifunctional-Adapted [rcp26socam / rcp60socam / rcp85socam]	even-aged clearcut transition to mixed forest with piab, bepe and soau	Fasy, piab, bepe, soau	stem	above above above above above above above above below below	20% BA	120	5 10 15 20 25 30 35 50 65 80 95 110	Fasy + NR 30% piab, 5% bepe, 3% soau	6200 + natural regeneration (3000 piab, 500 bepe 300 soau)	2	0.35 (0.25-0.5)	0.6	3	

Table 15: Detailed management schedule for Solling-beech. *Ini* = Initialization data, *HM* = Historic Management, *FM* = Future Management, *TB*=Thinning from below, *TA* = Thinning from above, *H*= Harvest, *P*=Planting

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	FM16	FM17	FM18	FM19	FM20	FM21	Remarks	
Current Generic	1967	1968-2014	2015	2016	2031	2046	2061	2076	2091	...	2156	2157	2172	...	2297	2298									maximum age extended a bit to match local management during observed period
		T	H	P	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	TA30	H	P	TA30	TA30	H	P									
Current Site-specific	1967	1968-2014	2020	2021	2026	2031	2036	2041	2046	2051	2056	2071	2086	2101	2116	2131	2141	2142	...	2262	2263	...	2298		
		T	H	P	TA20	TB20	TB20	H	P		H	P		TA20											
Bioenergy	1967	1968-2014	2020	2021	2066	2111	2112	2157	2202	2203	2248	2293	2294	2339											
		T	H	P	TB30																				
HWP	Same as Current Site Specific																								
Multifunctional-Adapted	1967	1968-2014	2020	2021	2026	2031	2036	2041	2046	2051	2056	2071	2086	2101	2111	2112	...	2202	2203	...	2293	...	2304		management for fasy & psme
		T	H	P	TA20	TB20	TB20	H	P	...	H	P	...	H	...	TA20									
Multifunctional-Adapted	1967	1968-2014	2020	2021	2026	2031	2036	2041	2046	2051	2056	2071	2086	2101	2116	2131	2141	2142	...	2262	2263	...	2298		Management for piab, fasy, bepe, soau
		T	H	P	TA20	TB20	TB20	H	P	...	H	P	...	TA20											

Solling-spruce

Table 16: Management guidelines for Solling-spruce.

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	piab	stem	below	30% BA	120	15 30 45 60 75 90 105	piab	2250 (2000-2500)	2	0.35 (0.3-0.4)	na	7	The actual stand was planted in 1891 on a former meadow. Until begin of measurements in 1966, the stand was regularly thinned. All figures in table are estimates.; stem count in 2014: 290
No management [nosoc]	na	piab	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	even-aged clearcut	piab	stem	above above above above above above above above below below	15% BA	120	5 10 15 20 25 30 35 50 65 80 95 110	piab	3000 (2500-3500)	2	0.35 (0.25-0.5)	0.6	3	
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	even-aged clearcut	piab	stem+ branches	below	25% BA	60	30	piab	3000 (2500-3500)	2	0.35 (0.25-0.5)	0.6	3	
HWP [rcp26sochwp / rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]	same as Current Site-specific													

Multifunctional-Adapted [rpc26soca / rpc60soca / rpc85soca]	even-aged clearcut transition to mixed forest with fasy, bepe and soau	piab, fasy, bepe, soau	stem	above above above above above above above above below below	15% BA	120	5 10 15 20 25 30 35 50 65 80 95 110	piab + NR 12% fasy, 5% bepe, 3% soau	2400 + NR (360 fasy, 150 bepe, 90 soau)	2	0.35 (0.25-0.5)	0.6	3	
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Table 17: Detailed management schedule for Solling-spruce. *Ini* = Initialization data, *HM* = Historic Management, *FM* = Future Management, *TB*=Thinning from below, *TA* = Thinning from above, *H*= Harvest, *P*=Planting

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	FM16	FM17	FM18	FM19	FM20	Remarks	
Current Generic	1967	1968-2014	2024	2025	2040	2055	2070	2085	...	2145	2146	2161	...	2266	2267	...								maximum age extended a bit to match local management during observed period
		T	H	P	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	TB30	H	P	TB30	TB30	H	P	TB30								
Current Site-specific	1967	1968-2014	2020	2021	2026	2031	2036	2041	2046	2051	2056	2071	2086	2101	2116	2131	2141	2142	...	2262	...	2298		
		T	H	P	TA15	TB15	TB15	H	P	...	H	...	TA15											
Bioenergy	1967	1968-2014	2020	2021P	2051	2081	2082	2112	2142	2143	2173	2203	2204	2234	2264	2265	2295	2325						
		T	H	P	TB25	H	P	TB25	H	P	TB25	H	P	TB25	H	P	TB25	H						
HWP	Same as Current Site-specific																							
Multifunctional-Adapted	1967	1968-2014	2020	2021	2026	2031	2036	2041	2046	2051	2056	2071	2086	2101	2116	2131	2141	2142	...	2262	...	2298	piab, fasy, bepe, soau	
		T	H	P	TA15	TB15	TA15	H	P	...	H	...	TA15											

Soro

Table 18: Management guidelines for Soro.

Scenario	Silvicultural system	Species	Harvest type [stem / branches]	Thinning type	Intensity	Rotation length [years]	Thinning frequency	Replanting species	Planting density	Planting age [years]	Planting seedling height [m]	Planting DBH [cm]	Age when DBH is reached [years]	Remarks
Current generic ISIMIP [2005soc]	even-aged clearcut	fasy	stem	above	30% BA	140	15 30 45 60 75 90 105 120 135	fasy	6000	4	0.82	na	6	Planted in 1921, stem count in 288 ha-1 in 2010, (Wu et al. 2013)
No management [nosoc]	na	fasy	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	allow any NR of species formerly present on plot
Current Site-specific [2005socsite]	sheltercut with NR	fasy	stem	below below below below below below below below below above above above above	20% 20% 20% 20% 10% 10% 10% 10% 10% 10% 10% 10% 10% BA	140 (keep a few shelter trees until age 160, if possible)	15 20 25 30 35 45 50 60 70 80 90 105 120	fasy	6000 from NR	2	0.4	na	7	at age 70 move to Future crop tree management, models could simulate as thinning from above because all trees have similar size anyway, overall this is a strategy to manage for high quality timber (veneer)
Bioenergy [rcp26socbe / rcp60socbe / rcp85socbe]	even-aged clearcut	fasy	stem+ branches	below	20% BA	100	15 30 45 60 75 90	fasy	5000	2	0.4	na	7	

HWP [rcp26sochwp / rcp60sochwp / rcp85sochwp]	even-aged clearcut	fasy	stem	below	20%	120	15	fasy	6000	2	0.4	na	7	planting for quality
				below	20%		20							
				below	20%		25							
				below	20%		30							
				below	20%		35							
				below	10%		45							
				below	10%		50							
				below	10%		60							
				below	10%		70							
				above	10%		80							
				above	10%		90							
				above	10% BA		105							
Multifunctional-Adapted [rcp26soca / rcp60soca / rcp85soca]	even-aged clearcut	fasy + psme	stem	below	20%	140	15	fasy, psme	4000 fasy, 2000 psme	fasy 2, psme 4	both 0.4	na	7	transition to mixed forest with clear-cut, Douglas-fir at age 70 move to Future crop tree management, models could simulate as thinning from above because all trees have similar size anyway
				below	20%		20							
				below	20%		25							
				below	20%		30							
				below	20%		35							
				below	10%		45							
				below	10%		50							
				below	10%		60							
				below	10%		70							
				above	10%		80							
				above	10%		90							
				above	10%		105							
above	10% BA	120												

Table 19: Detailed management schedule for Soro. *Ini* = Initialization data, *HM* = Historic Management, *FM* = Future Management, *TB*=Thinning from below, *TA* = Thinning from above, *H*= Harvest, *P*=Planting. Some GCM data only starts in 1950, hence for future runs, you have to initialize these forests at the first time step after 1949 (i.e. 1950 for Soro). For the historical validation runs you can start with the first available stand initialization.

Name	Ini	HM	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	FM6	FM7	FM8	FM9	FM10	FM11	FM12	FM13	FM14	FM15	FM16	FM17	FM18	FM19	FM20	FM21	Remarks	
Current Generic	1944	1945-2010	2020	2035	2050	2061	2062	2077	2092	---	2202	2203	2218	...											
		T	TA30	TA30	TA30	H	P	TA30	TA30	TA30	H	P	TA30												
Current Site-specific	1944	1945-2010	2026	2041	2061	2062	2077	2082	2087	2092	2097	2107	2112	2122	2132	2142	2152	2167	2182	2202	2203	...	2308		
		T	TA10	TA10	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB10	TB10	TB10	TB10	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	H	P	...	TA10		
Bioenergy	1944	1945-2010	2021	2022	2037	2052	2067	2082	2097	2112	2122	2123	2138	2153	2168	2183	2198	2213	2223	2224	2314			
		T	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	H	P	...	TB20			
HWP	1944	1945-2010	2026	2041	2042	2057	2062	2067	2072	2077	2087	2092	2102	2112	2122	2132	2147	2162	2163	...	2283	...	2304		
		T	TA10	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB10	H	P	...	H	...	TB20								
Multifunctional-Adapted	1944	1945-2010	2026	2041	2061	2062	2077	2082	2087	2092	2097	2107	2112	2122	2132	2142	2152	2167	2182	2202	2203	...	2308		
		T	TA10	TA10	H	P	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB20	TB10	TB10	TB10	TB10	TA10	TA10	TA10	TA10	H	P	...	TA10		

Table 20 Codes for management, species, disturbance names and dbh classes as used in protocol (species, dist-name, dbhclass).

Long name	Short name
Thinning	T
Thinning from above removing XX% of Basal Area	TAXX
Thinning from below removing XX% of Basal Area	TBXX
Thinning of random individuals for structural diversity (XX of Basal Area)	TXX
Harvest	H
Planting/Regeneration	P
Natural Regeneration	NR
Fagus sylvatica	fasy
Quercus robur	quro
Quercus petraea	qupe
Pinus sylvestris	pisy
Picea abies	piab
Pinus pinaster	pipi
Larix decidua	lade
Acer platanoides	acpl
Eucalyptus globulus	eugl
Betula pendula	bepe
Betula pubescens	bepu

Long name	Short name
Robinia pseudoacacia	rops
Fraxinus excelsior	frex
Populus nigra	poni
Sorbus aucuparia	soau
Pseudotsuga Menzies	psme
Quercus pubescens	qupu
Abies alba	abal
C3 grass	c3gr
hard woods	hawo
fire	fi
wind	wi
insects	ins
drought	dr
grazing	graz
diseases	dis
DBH-class_<X>-<X+5>*	dbh-c<X>
DBH-class_>140*	dbh-c140

*the boundaries of the dbh classes should interpreted as follows: dbh-class-0-5 = 0 to<5 5 cm; dbh-class-5-10 =5 to<10 cm, etc. The dbh class dbh-c140 includes all trees of 140cm dbh and larger.